
Development of a Recommendation System and Data Analysis in Personalized Medicine: An Approach towards Healthy Vascular Aging.

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Abstract Understanding early vascular aging (EVA) has become crucial for preventing adverse cardiovascular events. To this respect, recent AI-based risk clustering models offer early detection strategies focused on healthy populations, yet their complexity limits clinical use. Therefore, this work introduces a novel recommendation system (RS) embedded a web app to assess and mitigate EVA risk, guiding patients towards improved cardiovascular health. This system relied on an approach of calculating distances in multidimensional spaces and cost functions for the personalized optimization of recommendations, along with a system for categorizing the intensity levels of the recommendations. RS showed high efficiency in identifying and visualizing individuals at high risk of EVA among healthy patients, using the IA-based algorithm. Additionally, the system corroborated its consistency and reliability in generating personalized recommendations among different levels of granularity, emphasizing its focus on moderate

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or low intensity recommendations. This tool could significantly aid healthcare professionals in their daily analysis, improving the prevention and management of cardiovascular diseases.

Keywords: Vascular Aging; Recommendation Systems; Risk Assessment; Informatics Tool; Personalized Medicine

1. Introduction

Early Vascular Aging (EVA) is increasingly being recognized as a critical factor in the assessment of cardiovascular risk, representing a growing area of interest in preventive and clinical medicine (3). This condition, characterized by an accelerated deterioration of vascular health, manifests earlier than expected in the natural course of human aging and is significantly associated with an increased risk of adverse cardiovascular events, such as arrhythmia or stroke (1; 2). The concept of EVA is based on a series of clinical and biochemical parameters that reflect vascular function and structure, including indicators such as arterial stiffness, pulse pressure, and markers of inflammation and metabolism (3). Understanding EVA is crucial, not only for its ability to act as an early predictor of cardiovascular diseases but also for its potential to guide more effective preventive and therapeutic interventions. Furthermore, EVA may help elucidate the current gap between the predictions made by traditional cardiovascular risk models and the actual prevalence of cardiovascular diseases, offering a more refined and comprehensive approach to cardiovascular health assessment and management (3).

The challenge in modeling EVA mostly comes from the absence of a universal gold standard against which predictive models can be validated. Traditionally, studies in the literature have considered adverse cardiovascular events as the gold standard, focusing predominantly on populations already manifesting illness rather than on healthy individuals at risk (3). However, this approach means a significant lack in preventive strategies, particularly for identifying and managing individuals who have not yet shown clinical symptoms but are on the trajectory towards cardiovascular diseases. Indeed, to achieve a sustainable, efficient, and cost-effective future in healthcare, it is necessary a transition from a disease-centric culture to one that emphasizes prevention and the promotion of health (5).

In this context, our research team has pioneered the development of an unsupervised predictive Artificial Intelligent (IA) model for EVA that offers new insights into cardiovascular risk in populations not yet affected by evident diseases (3). Capable of predicting the risk of EVA in healthy individuals, our model shifts the focus from treatment to prevention. It is also worth noting this algorithm has been validated using external risk variables such as diabetes, cholesterol or smoking habits among others, thus enhancing its reliability and applicability in a clinical context (4).

Nevertheless, the inherent complexity of AI algorithms poses a significant challenge, as its implementation and correct interpretation requires a deep understanding of statistics and data analysis, thus limiting its accessibility to most

healthcare professionals. This barrier highlights the imperative need for a medical application, which could integrate our predictive EVA model, and guide clinicians with patient-tailored interventions. Frequently, the determination of the most suitable type of intervention for each patient is facilitated through the use of recommender systems (5). These systems are employed to deliver feedback and suggestions regarding health status and health behaviors, and encompassing areas such as lifestyle (6), nutrition (7), obesity (8), diabetes (9), or drug side effects (10), among others.

Therefore, the aim of this paper is to design and develop a recommendation system aimed at guiding clinical staff in their decision-making for the prevention of EVA. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time this approach has been proposed in the scientific literature. By introducing several clinical variables in the IA model, this work proposes a visual risk measurement system, together with a cost function algorithm, to guide the patient from a state of risk to the Health Vascular Aging (HVA) state in the fastest and safest way possible. This will be achieved through a mathematical approach that will adjust the input variables, supported by a recommendation system based on collaborative filtering scheme (11). Finally, the provided recommendations will be validated to confirm the system's coherence and effectiveness.

2. Method

2.1. Design and Validation of Clustering Model

To construct the IA model, an unsupervised K-means algorithm was employed to analyze a set of key clinical and biochemical parameters (3). Specifically, The algorithm was trained using a set of 390 healthy subjects, where 4 variables were measured for each subject: Pulse Pressure (PP), Pulse Wave Velocity (PWV), Glycated Hemoglobin (HbA1c), and Advanced Glycation End Products (AGEs). These variables showed to conform a construct by using a factorial confirmatory analysis, and each one of them proved to be a risk index of cardiovascular disease in isolation (3). After of recollection, data was normalized using z-score to ensure information comparability and consistency. Then, the K-means algorithm was utilized to stratify the data into distinct groups. Different strategies were used to determine the optimal number of conglomerates, resulting optimal identification of two primary risk clusters, which were labeled as HVA and EVA conglomerates.

Furthermore, the validation of the model was conducted through the comparison of the identified clusters with external cardiovascular risk factors (4). This external validation proved crucial for verifying the robustness and clinical relevance of the model. Indeed, it was observed that the risk groups identified by the algorithm significantly correlated with these traditional risk factors. To this respect, 4 groups of variables were evaluated, consisting of (IVAN, NECESITO QUE PONGAS AQUI UNA FRASE). Figure 1 shows a 2-D representation of the distribution of patients across the HVA and EVA risk conglomerates.

Figure 1. Graphical representation of patient dispersion using a 2-D Principal Component Transformation, across the two risk clusters: EVA and HVA

2.2. Visualizing Clinical Positions Relative to Healthy Vascular Aging

Once conformed risk stratification, the health state of each patient was evaluated by computing the distance between each one of its variables and its corresponding HVA cluster centroid using the Euclidean Distance (12). Mathematically, the distance d between a multidimensional sample point formed by the four input variables $v = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n)$ and the HVA centroid $c = (c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n)$ can be computed as:

$$d(v, c) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (v_i - c_i)^2} \quad (1)$$

To represent these multidimensional distances in a more intuitive way, a polar coordinate system was considered forming a radar visualization approach. Thus, the computed distances for each variable were mapped to distinct polar angles (0° , 90° , 180° , and 270°). This assignment corresponds to the four key variables: HbA1c, PP, AGEs and PWV respectively, such that the magnitude of each distance was plotted at its respective angle, forming a polygon when connected. To this respect, the area and shape of this polygon provided a visual representation of the patient's health state at glance. A larger area or extended polygonal shape indicates a greater deviation from the healthy state. This method allows for an immediate visual assessment of a patient's health status in relation to the ideal HVA condition, with each axis offering specific insights into different health parameters. Figure 2 displays the graphical representation of two random patients' clinical data using the radar chart method. Specifically, Figure 2(a) represents a patient falling into the EVA group and colored in red, while Figure

2(b) depicts a patient categorized within the HVA group and colored in green. It is worth noting that negative values on the charts indicate that the patient's measurements are healthier than the centroid of the HVA cluster such that these values are plotted towards the center of the chart, reducing the polygon's area.

Figure 2. Visual representation of the health status of two patients in (a) EVA and (b) HVA, considering the multidimensional distance to the HVA centroid

2.3. Optimization Pathways for Patient Variable Adjustment towards Healthy Vascular Aging

To modify patient variables towards a healthier state, a cost function $f(v)$ was implemented to evaluate potential pathways from EVA to HVA. $f(v)$ combines the Euclidean distance to the centroid of HVA with a penalty term λ that accounts for the magnitude of changes in the clinical variables, mathematically defined as:

$$f(\mathbf{v}) = \sum_{i=1}^n (v_i - c_i)^2 + \lambda \sum_{i=1}^n (v_i - v_{i,\text{original}})^2 \quad (2)$$

where v_i represents the vector of the patient's variables, c_i is the vector of the HVA centroid, $v_{i,\text{original}}$ are the original values of the patient's variables, and λ is the factor that regulates the penalty for changes in the variables. In this respect, the optimization process is tailored to each patient's unique clinical situation by iteratively adjusting the value of λ . Thus, this approach begins with a high λ value to ensure initial conservative changes, which is then gradually decreased to allow for more significant adjustments as needed. The dynamic tuning of λ serves to modulate the penalty for changes in clinical variables, ensuring that the optimization does not enforce uniform changes but rather adapts to the individual circumstances of each patient. The process continues until a transition from the EVA to the HVA cluster is observed, signifying a shift toward a healthier state as defined by the model. Moreover, dynamically

adjusting λ ensures that the balance between moving closer to the optimal health state and avoiding excessive and potentially unsafe changes in clinical variables is maintained throughout the optimization. This approach enables the estimation of the magnitude and direction of changes required in each input variable, thus laying the groundwork for a tailored recommender system.

2.4. Design of Recommender System

To construct a patient-tailored recommendation system, a quantitative approach was adopted, computing the changes in distance from the initial to the optimized state as derived from the cost function optimization defined in Section 2.3. The methodology entailed the computation of the 95th percentile for the change in distance of each clinical variable across the patient cohort. This percentile serves as a benchmark, representing a change threshold that encapsulates the significant yet realistic adjustments for the majority of the population, while effectively excluding outliers. Thus, the percentage change for each variable $\Delta\%(v)$ can be calculated as:

$$\Delta\%(v) = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{D_{\text{initial}}(v) - D_{\text{optimized}}(v)}{P_{95}(v)} \right) \times 100, & \text{if } D_{\text{initial}}(v) > 0 \\ 0, & \text{if } D_{\text{initial}}(v) \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $D_{\text{initial}}(v)$ represents the initial distance of variable v from the HVA centroid for a patient, $D_{\text{optimized}}(v)$ indicates the optimized distance after the application of the cost function optimization and $P_{95}(v)$ represents the 95th percentile of change for that variable across the patient cohort. Finally, based on $\Delta\%(v)$, outcomes were stratified into different levels of recommendation granularity that corresponded to the intensity of the proposed interventions.

In those instances where the percentage change $\Delta\%(v)$ for any variable was less or equal to zero, indicating that the initial distance for that variable was already healthier than the HVA centroid, the system was not issue any recommendations. This ensures that recommendations are reserved only for those instances where a patient's health status can be realistically improved, thereby avoiding unnecessary or redundant interventions for patients who are already at an optimal health state in specific variables.

2.5. Determination of Optimal Recommendation Levels and System Validation

To discern the optimal number of recommendation intensity levels for the system, various configurations were assessed, incrementally adjusting the number of recommendation levels from 3 to 6. The configurations were systematically analyzed based on different $\Delta\%(v)$, ranging from 0 to 100, as detailed in Table 1. The analysis also incorporated a specific no recommendation level, which was particularly designated for instances where the initial assessment metric, denoted as D_{initial} , was less than zero. As can be observed, the greater the $\Delta\%(v)$, the higher the associated intensity of the recommendation, and the greater the number of intensity levels, the more detailed or granular the recommendations.

Table 1. $\Delta\%(v)$ ranges and intensity of recommendations for different levels of granularity.

$\Delta\%(v)$	6 Levels	5 Levels	4 Levels	3 Levels
≤ 0	No Rec.	No Rec.	No Rec.	No Rec.
[0, 20]	Mild	-	-	-
[20, 40]	Moderate	-	-	-
[40, 60]	Normal	-	-	-
[60, 80]	Intense	-	-	-
[80, 100]	Very Intense	-	-	-
[0, 25]	-	Moderate	-	-
[25, 50]	-	Normal	-	Normal
[50, 75]	-	Intense	-	-
[75, 100]	-	Very Intense	-	Intense
[0, 33]	-	-	Mild	-
[33, 66]	-	-	Normal	-
[66, 100]	-	-	Intense	-

Furthermore, with the aim of validating the recommendation system, an extensive examination to discern the distribution and categorization of patients within the context of the generated unique recommendations was conducted. Thus, depending on $\Delta\%(v)$, the number of unique recommendations provided for a cohort of 390 patients was computed. This analytical approach was based in the premise that a robust recommendation system should inherently exhibit the capability to offer congruent recommendations for patients bearing similar clinical variables, such that the system should maintain consistency across patient recommendations.

To corroborate this consistence, scatter plot visualizations were used to elucidate the clustering patterns of patients according with the received recommendations. This visualization technique assisted to reveal the inherent grouping of patients, allowing for an intuitive understanding of the distribution of recommendations across the patient population. Given the multidimensional behaviour of this approach, a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed on the data to allow the visualization. This step transformed the complexity of the data into its two principal components, thus reducing dimensionality while preserving the intrinsic structure of the data. The PCA scatter plots then provided a concise visual representation of how patients were systematically grouped, reflecting how the recommendation system aligned patients with similar clinical profiles into coherent clusters (13).

Furthermore, to assist in the decision process regarding the optimal number of recommendation levels to provide, three statistical indices were calculated, that are the Calinski-Harabasz index, the Davies-Bouldin index, and the Silhouette index. The Calinski-Harabasz index measures the ratio of the variance between clusters to the variance within clusters, serving as an indicator of cluster tightness and separation (14). Higher values of this index suggest that the clusters are well-delineated and compact, implying a clear distinction between different patient groupings. On the other hand, the Davies-Bouldin index reflects the average similarity between each cluster and its most similar cluster (15). In this context, lower values are desirable, as they indicate that the clusters are well-separated and distinct, with minimal overlap between them.

Moreover, the Silhouette index calculates how similar an object is to its own cluster compared to other clusters, offering insight into the cohesion and separation of the clusters (16). A higher Silhouette score indicates that patients are well-matched to their own cluster and poorly matched to neighboring clusters, thus reinforcing the appropriateness of the assigned clusters. In the context of this recommendation system, a positive Silhouette index would signify that patients with similar clinical profiles are grouped together consistently, affirming the system's capability to provide coherent and targeted recommendations.

3. Results

3.1. Visual and Statistical Analysis

Figure 3 presents the visual representation of the optimization method applied to two random patients, one from the EVA and the other from the HVA group. The radar chart depicts the distance of each patient's clinical variables from the HVA centroid before and after the optimization process. Specifically, Figure 3(b) shows the chart for the HVA patient with a green polygon, which represents the original state of the patient's variables. The green dotted lines represent the optimized state after the execution of the cost function, indicating in this case minor adjustments, as the patient's variables were already close to the ideal state.

Conversely, Figure 3(a) shows the chart for the EVA patient colored with a red polygon, indicating a greater initial distance from the HVA centroid. After optimization, illustrated by the green dotted lines, the polygon's area has decreased significantly, indicating that the patient's variables have moved closer to the HVA profile. To this respect, while all variables have experienced some degree of optimization, the most affected variables are AGEs and HbA1c, which were initially the most diseased variables. This indicates that the optimization pathway has effectively suggested changes that could potentially improve the patient's vascular health status, thus demonstrating the practical utility of the cost function in guiding clinical decisions towards achieving a healthier vascular aging state for patients.

Additionally, Table 2 provides a detailed comparison between the original and optimized distances for the input variables. As Shapiro-Wilks test corroborated

Figure 3. Visual representation of the health status of two patients in (a) EVA and (b) HVA, along with the distances optimized by the cost function, for health improvement .

Table 2. Median, Range, and p-value of the Original and Optimized Distances for the input Variables

Variable	Original state		Optimized state		p-value
	Median	Range	Median	Range	
PP	0.0552	(-4.38, 5.77)	0.0460	(-2.75, 2.35)	3.53×10^{-4}
HbA1c	0.3823	(-3.83, 4.69)	0.2932	(-3.19, 2.13)	4.60×10^{-21}
PWV	0.5435	(-1.01, 4.54)	0.3913	(-0.84, 1.62)	2.86×10^{-23}
AGEs	0.4395	(-1.52, 5.95)	0.2642	(-1.27, 2.24)	3.28×10^{-25}

the no normality of the data distribution, it presents the median and range (minimum and maximum values) for both the original and optimized scenarios. Notably, a decrease in the median values is observed post-optimization for all variables, indicating a shift towards more centralized values. Furthermore, the range of values for each variable narrows after optimization, reflecting a reduction in variability and a tighter clustering of data points. The p-values, derived from the Wilcoxon test for paired samples, were remarkable ($p \leq 0.005$), affirming the statistical significance of the differences observed before and after optimization of distances.

Finally, Figure 4 shows a comprehensive visual representation of the intensity levels of recommendations for the four variables. Each variable is color-coded distinctly across five recommendation levels (see Section 3.2), ranging from the least intense (light green) to the most intense (red). Visually, the distribution of recommendations across these variables appears remarkably balanced, indicating a detailed and equitable approach in the intensity of recommendations. To this respect, while each variable exhibits a unique distribution pattern, no single

Figure 4. Count of Recommendation Intensity Levels by Variable.

intensity level dominates for any variable. Hence, Chi-squared test revealed no significant differences in the distribution of these five recommendation levels among these variables, scoring a Chi-squared statistic and p-value of 8.04 and 0.530, respectively. This lack of significant disparity among recommendation levels suggest that the system prevents from exhibiting a disproportionate bias towards any particular variable when issuing recommendations.

3.2. Validation Analysis and Determination of Optimal Recommendation Levels

Figure 5 presents different PCA scatter plots regarding the four approaches with different levels of granularity proposed in Table 1 (see Section 2.5). Each plot illustrates the distribution of patients across unique recommendation clusters, where each cluster containing ten or more patients, is distinctly represented by unique colors and symbols. As the number of recommendation levels decreases from six (Figure 5a) to three (Figure 5d), a notable increase in the number of clusters containing more than 10 patients is observed, as depicted by the expanding legends. This phenomenon reflects the inherent consequence of reduced granularity, as fewer available recommendation levels, patients naturally collapse into broader categories, thus elevating the count of larger, more populated clusters. Conversely, when the recommendation levels are augmented, a proliferation of more finely divided clusters emerges, signifying a tailored approach to patient categorization.

Despite this increased detail in patient segmentation, the scatter plots reveal a visual consistency in the proximity of patients within the clusters. Thus, patients with comparable initial four variables are consistently grouped in close

Figure 5. Clustering of more than 10 patients along unique recommendations, using (a) 6 levels, (b) 5 levels, (c) 4 levels, and (d) 3 levels of granularity.

association with one another, regardless of the number of recommendation levels. This persistent pattern, visible across all levels of granularity, corroborates the recommendation system’s validity and robustness, as it confirms that the recommendation system is proficient in forming coherent clusters, highlighting that patients with similar characteristics receive similar recommendations.

Table 3. Analysis of patient dispersion with different number of recommendation levels.

# Recom. levels	# Unique recom.	# Unique clusters*	Calinski-Harabasz	Davies-Bouldin	Silhouette index
6	144	9	36.12	1.37	0.169
5	122	11	39.12	1.42	0.152
4	94	13	38.22	1.48	0.137
3	46	14	48.47	1.42	0.137

Table 3 provides a structured overview of the clustering quality assessments conducted at various levels of recommendation granularity. It delineates the number of unique recommendations, the count of clusters with more than ten

patients, and the values for three key metrics: the Calinski-Harabasz index, the Davies-Bouldin index, and the Silhouette score.

The results table showcases a trend where the Calinski-Harabasz index generally increases as the number of recommendation levels decreases, suggesting a trend toward more well-defined clusters. Starting with six levels of recommendations, where the Calinski-Harabasz score is at 36.12, this index peaks at 48.47 when the recommendation levels are reduced to three, indicating the most distinct cluster separation at the lowest granularity level examined. Correspondingly, clusters with more than ten patients increase from 9 to 14 as the recommendation levels are changed from six to three, highlighting a tendency for patients to aggregate into larger, more generalized groupings as the number of unique recommendations decreases.

Conversely, the Silhouette score, starting at 0.169 for six recommendation levels, shows a downward trend as the levels decrease, settling at 0.137 for both four and three levels of recommendations. This suggests that while clusters become more distinct, the tightness of the clusters may not proportionally increase with fewer recommendation levels. Finally, the Davies-Bouldin index fluctuates slightly but does not exhibit a consistent trend, varying between 1.37 and 1.48 across the different levels, which indicates variability in the average similarity between clusters. These changes reflect the complex balance between cluster separation, cohesion, and the granularity of the recommendation system.

4. Discussion

In recent years, recommendation systems have been widely used in various application areas, such as eCommerce (17), entertainment (18), or finances (19), among others. Thanks to advances in AI and data analysis, they are also being used intensively in personalized medicine, providing tailored recommendations in treatments, medications, and other health services (20; 21). In this work, a recommendation system based on collaborative filtering (22) is proposed for the first time to assess the risk of suffering from EVA, where the recommendations provided to patients are based on an unsupervised AI model, trained using the K-means algorithm(3).

The integration of AI in medical applications can lead to faster and more accurate diagnoses, optimize treatments, and improve patient outcomes by providing physicians with powerful, data-driven tools to inform and support their clinical decisions (23). However, there is a reluctance among physicians to trust and adopt something they do not fully understand and consider a 'black box' (29). For this reason, authors in the literature have highlighted the need to develop user-friendly tools for physicians that allow them to focus on clinical decision-making rather than the technical details of AI (28). In this work, the proposed AI system has been programmed into a computer application as can be seen in Figure 6, following some key design principles such as intuitiveness, ease of use, and interactivity (30).

To determine the intensity of the recommendations, an optimization system with an associated cost function has been developed, which allows transitioning

Figure 6. Web app prototype for health status visualization and recommendation proposal

a given patient from a state of EVA to a more optimal health state. These methodological techniques have previously been used in personalized medicine to improve medication efficacy, safety, and cost reduction (24; 25). In this work, the intensity of each intervention is categorized depending on the distance between original and optimized health status, resulting that recommendation system showed a clear predominance of moderate or medium interventions for the treatment of all input characteristics. This approach may be indicative of a carefully calibrated approach prioritizing incremental or moderated health improvements, which have been reported to be more effective and sustainable for long-term adherence compared to aggressive interventions (26; 27). Indeed, by using a penalty term in the cost function, a conservative strategy is being employed, where the system deliberately opts for less drastic interventions, and aiming to minimize potential risks or disruptions in patients' lives.

Furthermore, the granularity level of the recommendations was also evaluated, resulting in few differences between the clusters of patients receiving the same recommendation. In this case, the optimum approach is to propose a balance between cluster separation, cohesion, and the granularity of the recommendation system. Analysing the result, this threshold could be set at five levels of recommendation, where the system articulates 122 unique recommendations, providing a substantial degree of personalisation without delving into excessive granularity that could potentially obfuscate clinical decision-making. Moreover, the relatively high Calinski-Harabasz index at this level indicates well-defined and separated clusters. Similarly, the Davies-Bouldin index stands competitively, indicating that the spread within clusters is not overly pronounced relative to the separation between them. Moreover, the Silhouette index for five levels, remains reasonably indicative of a coherent clustering structure, where patients are closer

to others within their cluster than to those in neighboring clusters. Finally, from a clinical point of view, this granularity allows for addressing diverse patient profiles without introducing overwhelming complexity.

Additionally, it's crucial to acknowledge that when contemplating the visual interpretation of patient clustering within the same recommendation clusters, the representation might not encapsulate the full complexity of the underlying relationships. This restriction arises from the inherent limitations of dimensionality reduction techniques such as PCA, which can sometimes obscure the subtle details present in the original multi-dimensional space (31).

Finally, there are some issues that deserve certain consideration. On the one hand, the app developed for this work is a proof of concept of the integration of the AI and recommendation system. However, in the future, a user-centered app should be undertaken, which would involve going beyond the scope of this work, covering issues such as research and active user participation from the early stages of development (32) or the evaluation and ongoing support to improve user adherence to the app (33). On the other hand, the recommendation intensity levels for addressing interventions on each of the model's variables will be replaced in the future with a list of specific actions. To this end, a network meta-analysis study will be conducted, gathering scientific evidence on the most effective treatments that can reduce risk at different intensity levels.

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